

Abstract

Acupuncture for Radiation-Induced Xerostomia in Head and Neck Cancer Patients: A Randomised Controlled Pilot Study.

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Abstract

Background: Xerostomia (chronic dry mouth) is a debilitating side effect for patients undergoing radiotherapy for head and neck malignancies. This exploratory study aimed to objectively evaluate whether acupuncture improves salivary function and to determine if the therapeutic effects justify larger-scale clinical research.

Methods: A preliminary randomised, non-blinded, controlled clinical trial was conducted with a waiting-list control group. The study initially screened 33 patients treated at the Radiotherapy Service of Centro Hospitalar do Porto, Portugal, between October 2014 and May 2015. Following strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, 18 patients were randomly allocated to either an Experimental Group (EG), receiving eight acupuncture sessions, or a Control Group (CG) on a waiting list. Objective measures included sialometry (to measure salivary flow rates) and the modified Schirmer test. Quality of life (QoL) was assessed using the EORTC QLQ-C30 and the head and neck-specific QLQ-H&N35 modules.

Results: Comparative analysis between the groups revealed a statistically significant increase in overall salivary volume ($p < 0.001$). Specifically, the experimental group demonstrated significant improvements in both unstimulated salivary flow ($p = 0.001$) and stimulated salivary flow ($p = 0.011$). Subjective reports also indicated a significant reduction in dry mouth sensation ($p = 0.03$), with a positive trend observed across other radiotherapy-related symptoms.

Conclusions: These findings suggest that acupuncture may serve as an effective intervention for radiation-induced xerostomia. While the small sample size necessitates a cautious interpretation, the results indicate that the acupuncture protocol utilised can successfully enhance salivary production and improve the quality of life for head and neck cancer survivors. Further robust, multi-centre trials are warranted.

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B)

- A) Salivary flow (ml), with and without salivary induction according to the sialometry test, at baseline and after 4 weeks within the experimental group.
- B) Salivary flow (ml), with and without salivary induction, according to the sialometry test, at baseline and after 4 weeks within the control group.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Xerostomia; Radiotherapy; Head and Neck Cancer; Salivary Flow; Quality of Life.

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